

Protocol for human skin biopsy processing

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If protocol is used, please cite as follows:

P Karlsson, AT Møller, TS Jensen, JR Nyengaard. Epidermal nerve fiber length density estimation using global spatial sampling in healthy subjects and neuropathy patients. *Journal of Neuropathology and Experimental Neurology*, 2013; 72:186-93 doi: 10.1097/NEN.0b013e318284e849.

Important considerations before performing skin biopsy

1. Is the person allergic to lidocaine?
2. Is the person on stronger anticoagulants? If yes, excess bleeding is to be expected. Consider using a gelatin sponge to stop the bleeding if the biopsy should be taken. The patient should not have any active foot ulcers or a history of very problematic wound healing.
3. Only use Zamboni's or 2% PLP fixative, as formalin blocks the antigenic determinant sites.
4. Disinfect the skin biopsy site carefully using alcohol wipes, use only sterile, disposable instruments and wear sterile gloves.
5. Inject 0.5 to 1.0 mL 2% lidocaine subcutaneously.
6. Fixing time (store in fridge) should be overnight but not exceed 24 hours for IENFD analysis using PGP 9.5 antibody.
7. Avoid contacting epidermis when taking the biopsy using forceps and handle the tissue gently without crushing it to preserve the integrity of the tissue layers. Transfer the biopsy directly to fixative.
8. Place a larger band aid over the wound and give the patients extra to take home to change after bathing or when visually dirty. Instruct patient not to shower until the day after and not to swim before visible scab.
9. The morning after, wash the biopsy 2-3 times for couple of minutes using either TBS, PBS, or cryoprotectant. Once properly washed, tap up with cryoprotectant and store in fridge for minimum overnight and maximum 2 weeks.
10. Freeze the biopsy using OCT compound and store in -20°C for short term storage (< 6 months) or -80°C for long term storage (up to few years).
11. Adhering to standard hygiene practices significantly reduces the risk of complications, with the likelihood being quite low (approximately 1 in 1000). It is normal to observe clear serous fluid from the wound within the first 24-48 hours post-procedure. However, the presence of cloudy fluid, redness, and soreness around the wound site are unexpected and could indicate a potential complication, such as an infection.

Staining protocol for IENFD using PGP 9.5 antibody

This protocol is typical for immunocytochemistry studies, aiming to specifically localize proteins or antigens within skin sections using antibodies. Each step is designed to enhance the specificity and visibility of the target antigens while minimizing background staining and nonspecific binding.

Day 1: Preparation and Primary Antibody Incubation

1. Use of 96 well tissue culture plates: Ensures sections remain submerged throughout the process.
2. Rinsing: Sections are rinsed twice in Tris-buffered saline (TBS) for 10 minutes at room temperature to remove any preservatives or storage medium.
3. Triton X-100 treatment and blocking:
 - Incubate sections in TBS containing 0.5% powdered milk, 1.0% Triton X-100, and 4% normal serum (matching the species origin of the secondary antibody) for 1 hour on a shaker table at room temperature. This step permeabilizes the cells and blocks non-specific binding sites.
4. Primary Antibody Application:
 - Place sections in TBS with 0.5% Triton X-100 and 2% normal serum, adding the primary antibody at the desired dilution. Incubate overnight.

Day 2: Secondary antibody application and visualization

1. Rinsing: Begin by rinsing the sections twice in TBS for 10 minutes at room temperature.
2. Secondary antibody:
 - Incubate sections in TBS containing 0.5% Triton X-100 and 2% normal serum for 1 hour at room temperature on a shaker table. Add biotinylated secondary antibody at a 1:100 dilution, or your preferred dilution.
 - Follow with two 10-minute rinses in TBS.
3. Methanol/Hydrogen Peroxide treatment:
 - To quench endogenous peroxidases, incubate sections in a mixture of 33.3% methanol/PBS with 3.3% H₂O₂ for 30 minutes at room temperature on a shaker table.
4. Vector ABC (Avidin-Biotin Complex):
 - Prepare and apply the A:B mix to the sections for 1 hour at room temperature on the shaker table, followed by two 10-minute rinses in PBS.
5. Vector SG Substrate kit application:
 - Prepare the mix just before use due to light sensitivity. Apply to the sections for visualization of the antigen-antibody complex.

Slide Preparation and Counterstaining

- Label and prepare slides with a PBS/Triton X-100 mix.
- Line up the biopsies on a slide and air dry for at least 30 minutes.
- Soak dried slides in tap water for 1 minute to remove salt residues.
- Counterstain with eosin for 5-8 seconds (timing varies based on the eosin's strength and personal preference), followed by dehydration through alcohol gradients.
- Clear in xylene and apply a coverslip for preservation and viewing.